

Staff Training as a Factor Influencing Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated staff training as a factor influencing Service Delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State. The survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study is made up of library personnel in different academic libraries in Ondo state. Total enumeration sampling technique was used to capture a total of 227 library staff. A structured questionnaire was used for the study with a retrieval of 208 copies which constitute 91% return rate. Data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The findings of the study revealed the types of training programmes mostly available to library staff in the study area as computer based training, Workshop and seminar, Conferences attendance and Formal Professional education while study visit and coaching/mentoring were least. The study further showed that staff training significantly influence service delivery in academic libraries in ondo state ($r = 0.335$ and $r^2 = 0.112$ or 11.2% is found to be significant at $P < 0.05$). and the challenges of staff training in the study area are lack of financial resources, excessive workload and lack of interest of the management towards training programmes . The study therefore recommended that library leadership should develop sustainable training model and academic institutions should adequately fund the library for this purpose .

Keywords: staff training, job performance, academic libraries, library staff, ondo state

Introduction

Academic Library not only provides access to information resources but, also facilitates and disseminates knowledge hence, a cornerstone entity within the educational landscape. As of

Received: 22July 2025

Revised: 26 July 2025

Accepted: 29 July 2025

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516

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.16777551](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16777551)

recent, academic libraries have evolved significantly due to advancement in information technology and increase demands for efficient information services (Ogunode & Samuel, 2022). Consequently, the foregoing has made the quality of service delivery in academic libraries to become a central concern for library management, users, and stakeholders at large. However, the effectiveness of libraries largely depends on the performance of their staff and this hinges on staff training as a crucial factor that impacts on service delivery and overall performance of academic libraries (Alala et al., 2022).

Service delivery in academic libraries as noted by Akpokodje and Lawal (2015) encompasses a range of activities including reference and research assistance, material circulation, interlibrary loans, information literacy instruction, and digital resource management that are designed to provide timely and efficient access to information resources, user satisfaction and overall library effectiveness. Enhancing service delivery is a predictor of overall service effectiveness that requires a well-coordinated effort involving training staff members to meet library user needs (Gyau et al. (2021). The foregoing implies that staff training affects the quality of services that can be delivered and provided to library users with continually improved direct and indirect professional assistance that keep pace with the evolving information needs of 21st-century by library users. Hence, the need for library authorities to seek ways to enhance these services of librarians constantly (Akpokodje and Lawal, 2015)

Statement of the Problem

The field of library science is constantly evolving, with new tools, technologies, and best practices emerging regularly. Training opportunities, such as workshops, webinars, conferences, and professional certifications, provide staff with the knowledge and skills they need to stay current in their field (Ijeh et al., 2024)

Despite the recognized importance of staff training, there is a growing concern about the ability of academic libraries in Ondo State to adequately support their staff in this area due to common challenges such as inadequate funding, limited infrastructure and inadequate technology and digital resources among others (Ademodi and Adepoju, 2009). This not only leads to decline in service delivery but it negatively impacted users experience and overall library performance and underscores the need for continuous staff training to ensure effective service delivery.

Given the critical role of academic libraries in fostering academic achievement and research excellence, it is essential to explore how staff training has influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State.

Objectives of the study

This study explored how staff training has influenced service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. identify the types of training available to library staff in academic libraries in Ondo State.
2. determine the extent to which library staff benefit from staff training in academic libraries in Ondo state.
3. identify the challenges mitigating effective staff training for effective and efficient library services delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state.
4. determine the impact of staff training on service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria?

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide this study;

1. What are the types of training that are available to library staff in academic libraries in Ondo State?
2. To what extent do library staff benefit from training programs in academic libraries in Ondo State?
3. What are the challenges of effective staff training in academic libraries in Ondo State?
4. What are the significant contributions of staff training to service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The null hypothesis raised to guide the conduct of this study and was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between staff training and service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Significance of the study

The effectiveness of service delivery is critically influenced by staff training (Abubakar, 2021). The findings of this study will provide valuable insights for library management, policymakers, and other stakeholders in the academic sector, helping to create a more efficient and responsive library system that meets the needs of its users.

The study will help academic institutions in Ondo State to understand how staff training affects the quality of library services. This knowledge can guide policies and decisions aimed at improving the operational effectiveness of their libraries. Moreover, this study will provide valuable insights into the current state of staff training, and help administrators identify areas that need improvement and develop strategies for enhancing staff performance and improving service delivery. In addition, the outcome of this study will inform policymakers on the importance of investing in the training of library staff to achieve the broader goal of academic excellence, the formulation of state or national policies that can enhance library services in higher education.

Finally, this study will contribute to the academic literature on library management and service delivery by providing empirical evidence on the role of staff training and development of strategies that will enhance staff performance, improve service quality, and ultimately support the academic objectives of these tertiary institutions in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Review of Literatures

Concept of Staff Training in Academic Libraries

The concept of staff training has evolved significantly over the past century.

In the late 20th century, the emergence of globalization and technological advancements further emphasized the need for continuous staff training, as organizations required highly skilled employees to remain competitive in a rapidly changing market (Nwofor et al., 2023).

In practice, staff training is a versatile tool that has been effectively applied across various industries and sectors, with the primary aim of enhancing employee performance, job

satisfaction, and overall organizational productivity (Abubakar et al., 2020). Staff training is not just a fundamental component of workforce development but also a critical driver of long-term organizational success (Okwu & Oporum, 2021). It is a carefully planned and structured approach designed to bridge the gap between the current capabilities of employees and the evolving demands of their roles (Ayoung, Baada, & Baayel, 2020).

Staff training is not a one-size-fits-all endeavor; it is customizable, with distinct section targeting different aspects of organization's needs. For example, in library sectors where rapid changes occur frequently, training needs to be continuously updated to keep employees abreast of new developments, ensuring that they remain competent and relevant in their field (Awogbami et al., 2021).

Concept of Service Delivery in Academic Libraries

Service delivery refers to the process of providing a service that meets the needs and expectations of users or clients. This process is crucial in all organizations, particularly in institutions like academic libraries, where the goal is to support research, learning, and knowledge dissemination. Moreover, service delivery significantly impacts the efficiency and effectiveness of organizations, particularly in libraries (Yaya, 2019) where it involves the offering of wide array of services ranging from access to physical and digital resources to research support, user assistance, and finally to managing library systems (McAlbert et al., 2022). As noted by Tella and Ibinaiye (2020), the capacity to provide high-quality service is contingent on a range of factors, including staff competence, the availability of resources, organizational structure, and the extent of user engagement.

As succinctly submitted, quality service delivery is not only about meeting users' immediate needs but also about anticipating future demands and continuously improving the services offered and this signifies ensuring that library resources, both physical and digital, are up-to-date, relevant, and accessible (Ayodeji et al., 2022). The foregoing as succinctly pointed out by Shonhe (2019), requires the integration of technology, such as online databases, automated cataloging, and mobile apps, to enhance user convenience and satisfaction. In addition, the increasing reliance on technology in service delivery as evident in academic libraries, where mobile technologies are transforming the way library services are provided to distance learning students and remote researchers has increase service delivery of academic libraries (Acheampong & Agyemang, 2021).

The foregoing succinctly pointed to the fact that service delivery in academic libraries encompasses a broad range of activities and processes aimed at fulfilling the diverse information needs of students, faculty, researchers, and other members of the academic community. It is the backbone of the library's role in supporting teaching, learning, and research, ensuring that users have timely access to relevant resources and receive the necessary support to effectively utilize these resources.

Concept of Staff training and Service Delivery in Academic Libraries

Staff training is a critical component in the effective delivery of services in academic libraries. In an era where technology is rapidly evolving and user expectations are increasing, staff training is widely recognized as an essential factor in improving service delivery in academic libraries.

According to Aina (2019), training helps staff acquire new skills, understand emerging technologies, and adopt best practices in library management and user support. Without proper training, library personnel may struggle to meet the diverse needs of users, especially in the rapidly changing information environment.

Moreover, in modern academic libraries, the increasing reliance on digital platforms and electronic resources necessitates that staff have a sound understanding of information technology. According to Eze (2020), staff exposed to training programs that focused on information literacy, database management, and digital cataloging significantly improve the ability of library personnel to offer efficient and effective services deliveries such as guiding users in accessing electronic resources, navigating databases, and using digital library tools effectively.

The above discussion has shown that staff training is essential for improving service delivery in academic libraries. It enhances the technical skills, knowledge, and confidence of library personnel, enabling them to provide better user services, support research activities, and manage digital resources effectively. However, challenges such as limited funding, technological barriers, and time constraints can hinder the implementation of comprehensive training programs. To overcome these challenges, academic libraries must prioritize staff development by investing in tailored training programs, fostering a culture of continuous learning, and securing institutional support for professional growth. By addressing these challenges, libraries can ensure that their staff are well-equipped to meet the evolving needs of their users, thereby enhancing service delivery.

Theoretical Framework

Human Capital Theory

Various theories explain the role of training in the workplace, with most grounded in learning and human resource development frameworks. One of the key theories is the Human Capital Theory, which posits that investments in employees, through training, improve their productivity, thereby benefiting the organization (Becker, 1993). According to this theory, employees are viewed as valuable assets whose development is essential for long-term organizational success. Human Capital Theory developed by Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz (1964), underscores the importance of investing in employees' education, training, and development. It posits that such investments enhance workforce skills, knowledge, and competencies, leading to improved performance and productivity. This is particularly relevant for academic libraries, where the quality of service delivery hinges on staff capabilities. Human Capital Theory suggests that training programs are crucial for equipping library staff with the skills needed to address evolving user needs. With advancements in technology and digitization, library staff must manage digital collections, provide information literacy instruction, and offer personalized support. Enhanced competencies through training improve service delivery and align with the academic mission of libraries.

For example, a well-trained librarian can effectively manage electronic resources, helping users access information efficiently. Similarly, training in customer service skills can enhance user interactions, resulting in a better library experience. Thus, Human Capital Theory emphasizes the

importance of ongoing professional development for fulfilling the library's role in supporting teaching, learning, and research.

Thus, training is most effective when it engages employees in direct experiences, allowing them to reflect on their learning and apply it to practical situations (Kamselem et al., 2020). Furthermore, the use of reinforcement during training sessions and this can be effectively learnt through demonstrations and role models during training sessions (Fabunmi et al., 2023). In the application of new knowledge learnt, the design of the training program, the work environment, and individual learner characteristics must be considered. To enhance the likelihood of successful training, training must not only be relevant and practical but also support workplace culture whereby employees are encouraged to implement their newly acquired skills effectively. With this notion, maximum return on investment in training programs will be achieved and this translates into improved organizational performance.

While various scholars agree on the importance of staff training, there are differing perspectives on its most effective delivery. Anyaegbu & Wali (2023) argues that formalized training programs that are tied to organizational goals are most effective, as they ensure alignment between individual growth and business objectives. On the other hand, Godwin et al., (2020) emphasize the need for flexibility in training programs, suggesting that personalized learning paths can lead to better outcomes, especially in diverse and dynamic workplace environments. The importance of staff training and professional development for librarians is widely recognized in the literature. For instance, Adamu, Udoudoh, and Babalola (2023) emphasize that in-service training significantly enhances job performance among librarians in Nigerian universities. This highlights the critical role of well-structured training programs in equipping librarians with the skills necessary for effective performance.

Similarly, Anyaegbu and Wali (2023) demonstrate a direct relationship between training initiatives and job satisfaction. Their study reveals that librarians who participate in relevant training programs report higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation, which, in turn, translates into improved service delivery. This underscores the necessity of continuous professional development to sustain job motivation and satisfaction among library staff.

Empirical Studies

Research conducted by Ayodeji et al. (2022) demonstrated that libraries with structured training programs experience significant improvements in staff proficiency and service delivery. This study highlights how training equips library staff with essential skills and knowledge, enabling them to better manage library operations, respond to user inquiries, and support research activities. Further corroboration comes from Obaseki and Bakare (2022), who found that comprehensive training initiatives positively impact service quality by enabling staff to handle various aspects of library services more effectively. Their research underscores the importance of ongoing professional development in maintaining high service standards.

Maiwada and Obaseki (2018) support these findings by showing that training in new technologies and methodologies leads to notable improvements in service delivery. Their study indicates that well-trained staffs are better positioned to leverage new tools and systems to enhance library services. Joseph and Urhiewhu (2016) also emphasize the critical role of training

in enabling staff to manage diverse library functions and provide high-quality services. Despite these positive outcomes, the sustainability of training benefits poses a challenge.

Nkosi and Mkhize (2020) observed that while training in digital tools initially improved service quality, the absence of follow-up training resulted in a decline as technology continued to advance. This highlights the need for libraries to implement ongoing training programs that address evolving technological and user demands. Wanjiru and Khamisi (2019) further illustrate this point by emphasizing the importance of integrating ICT skills into training programs, particularly in managing digital resources and facilitating user access. This integration is crucial for maintaining service quality in the digital age, especially in regions with limited ICT infrastructure.

Ehinola and Akomolafe (2022) further support this view, arguing that continuous professional development is essential for librarians to adapt to the evolving demands of library services. Their findings indicate that ongoing training not only improves individual job performance but also contributes to the overall effectiveness of the library as an institution. This points to the dynamic nature of librarianship and the constant need for librarians to stay updated with new developments in their field. In a related study, Babalola et al. (2013) explore the connection between motivation and productivity, revealing that motivated librarians are more likely to engage in professional development activities. This correlation suggests that institutions should foster environments that promote both motivation and training, as these factors are interlinked and crucial for maximizing the productivity of library staff.

Godwin et al. (2020) stress the importance of innovative practices within libraries, asserting that staff training plays a vital role in fostering innovation. Regular training programs equip librarians with the skills and knowledge necessary to introduce and implement new ideas and services, thereby improving the quality of library services. This focus on innovation is particularly relevant in today's rapidly changing information landscape, where libraries must continuously evolve to meet user needs. Similarly, Ameyaw et al. (2021) highlight the role of effective training as a catalyst for enhancing library staff performance. Their study suggests that librarians who undergo training are more motivated, engaged, and productive, ultimately contributing to higher service quality in libraries.

The relationship between staff training and user satisfaction is also explored in the work of Isah et al. (2020), who demonstrate that training investments are directly correlated with improved service quality. This makes a strong case for prioritizing staff development initiatives, as they have a tangible impact on the overall satisfaction of library users. In addition to service quality, Awogbami et al. (2021) examine the role of training in knowledge management, noting that training in emerging technologies is essential for equipping librarians with the tools necessary to manage and disseminate knowledge effectively. This is particularly important in today's digital age, where technology plays an increasingly central role in the delivery of library services.

Methodology

This study adopted survey research design method. In doing so, 227 library personnel were purposively sampled from the academic libraries of twelve (12) tertiary institutions in Ondo State, Nigeria. (Table 1).

Received: 22 July 2025

Revised: 26 July 2025

Accepted: 29 July 2025

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522

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.16777551](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16777551)

Table1; List of Academic Institutions in Ondo State and Sampled Library Personnel

S/N	Institution	Population
1	Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko (AAUA)	38
2	Achievers University, Owo (AUO)	10
3	Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin (EU)	6
4	Wesley University, Ondo (WU)	4
5	Samaris University, Eti-Oro, Supare Akoko (SU)	3
6	Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA)	74
7	Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo	19
8	Federal College of Agriculture, Akure	11
9	Federal Polytechnic, Ile-Oluji (FPI)	11
10	Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa (OAUSTECH)	13
11	Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo (RUGIPO)	25
12	University of Medical Sciences, Ondo (UNIMED)	13
	Total	227

Source: Fieldwork 2025

Questionnaire was the instrument used for collection of data. Crombach’s alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to the staff and retrieved from them physically and via WhatsApp . 208 respondents returned copies of the questionnaire. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Finally, at $p= 0.05$, Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was employed to test the stated hypothesis and also used to examine the influence among variables.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What are the types of training programmes available to library personnel in academic libraries in Ondo State?

Table 2: Types Staff Training Programmes available to Library Personnel in Academic Libraries in Ondo State

S/ N	ITEMS	Mean Wight Values (MWVs)
1	Computer based training is a training method in my library	3.04
2	Workshop and seminars training is prevalent in my library	3.00
3	Self-instruction is the available means of training in my library	3.00
4	Conferences attendance is the source of training in my library	2.99
5	Formal Professional library education is	2.99

	the means of training in my library	
6	In- house training method is practiced in my library	2.90
7	Coaching or mentorship is the means of training in my library	2.82
8	Study Visit is the training method available in my library	2.65
	Grand Mean Weight Value (GMWV)=	2.92

Source: Fieldwork 2025

Table .2, depicts the summary of the analysis of the data collected on types of training programmes available to library personnel in academic libraries in Ondo State. The subjective notions of the respondents were converted to objective notions using Likerte scale conversion. Thereafter, the mean weight value method was used to determine relevant variables, and, doing so, variable whose mean is equal to or more than the Grand Mean Weight Value (GMWV) is accepted to be relevant and vice versa (Sunmola, 2018).

With a GMWV = 2.92 , the common types of training programmes available to library staff in academic libraries in Ondo State are; computer based training (MWV = 3.04), Workshop and seminars(MWV = 3.00), Self-instruction (MWV = 3.00), Conferences attendance (MWV =2.99), Formal Professional library education (MWV = 2.99). These types of training were accepted because their Grand Means are more than the GMWV of 2.92.

In- house training(MWV = 2.9), Coaching or mentorship (MWV = 2.82) and Study Visit (MWV =2.65) were rejected as prevailing types of training programmes available to library personnel in academic libraries in Ondo State because their Means are lesser to the GMWV of 2.92.

Research Question 2: To what extent do library staff benefit from training programe in academic libraries in Ondo state?

Table3: Staff Training and Effective Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Ondo State?

S/N	ITEMS	Mean Weight Values (MWVs)
1.	Training helps me to respond appropriately to needs and feelings of Library patrons	3.45
2.	Training helps me to be more creative	3.36
3.	Training has improved my service delivery skills	3.29
4.	It helps me to complete my tasks in a timely manner	3.25
5.	Training has enhance my digital skills and increase access to information by library users	3.25
6.	Training helps me work with others	3.23
7.	Staff training has increased the level of users satisfaction in my library.	3.10

Grand Mean Weight Value	3.28
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Table .3, depicts the summary of the analysis of the data collected on extent staff training had helped Liberians to make good service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state. The subjective notions of the respondents were converted to objective notions using Likerte scale conversion .Thereafter, the mean weight value method was used to determine relevant variables, and, doing so, variable whose mean is equal to or more than the GMWV is accepted to be relevant and vice versa (Sunmola, 2018).

With a GMWV = 3.28, the accepted extents that staff training had helped Liberians to make good service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state include but not limited to staff training had helped Liberians in academic libraries in Ondo to respond appropriately to the needs and feelings of Library patrons (MWV = 3.45), to be more creative (MWV = 3.36) and improved their service delivery skills (MWV = 3.29). These extent of staff training that have helped Liberians to make good service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state were accepted because their Ms were more than the GMWV of 3.28.

But, the fact that staff training had helped Liberians to make good service delivery such as helping librarians in academic libraries in Ondo state to complete their tasks in a timely manner (MWV = 3.25), enhancing their digital skills and increase access to information by library users (MWV = 3.25), helping them to work with others (MWV =3.23) and helping librarians to increased their level of users satisfaction (MWV = 3.1) were rejected among the extent that staff training had helped Library staff to make good service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state because their GMs are lesser to the GMWV of 3.28.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges mitigating effective staff training for effective and efficient library services delivery in academic libraries in Ondo state?

Table 4: Challenges of Staff Training in Academic Libraries in Ondo State.

S/ N	Items	Mean
1	Lack of financial resources is a setback to organizing training for personnel in my library	2.86
2	I found the staff development programs interesting	2.14
3	There is Lack of interest of management towards training	2.60

	programmes in my library	
4	There is no time to organize taff training in my library	2.35
5	Excessive workload makes my work difficult in the library.	2.73
6	Computer illiteracy hinders me from participating in training programmes in my library.	2.12
7	I am not interested in the training programmes in my library	2.00
	Grand Mean	2.40

Table 4 shows the summary of data collected on challenges of staff training in Academic Libraries in Ondo State. The subjective notions of the respondents were converted to objective notions using Likerts scale conversion .Thereafter, the mean weight value method was used to determine relevant variables, and, doing so, variable whose mean is equal to or more than the GMWV is accepted to be relevant and vice versa (Sunmola, 2018).

With a GMWV = 2.40, the accepted challenges of staff training in Academic Libraries in Ondo State are:lack of financial resources (MWV = 2.86), excessive workload (MWV = 2.73) and lack of interest of the management towards training programmes (MWV = 2.60). These challenges were accepted because their M values are more than the GMWV value of 2.40.

In the other vein, lack of time to organize staff training in my library (MWV =2.35), lack of interest in staff development programs (MWV =2.14), Computer illiteracy (MWV = 2.12) and lack of interest in library training programmes (MWV = 2.00) are not challenges to staff training in Academic Libraries in Ondo State.

Research Question 4: What are the significant contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria?

Table 5: Contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	Mean Weight Values (MWVs)
1	I am always punctual for work and appointments	3.50
2	I create new ideas to make service delivery easy	3.32
	I encourage my colleagues as a team on the quantity of work output	3.20
3	I am proficient in communication skills	3.28
4	Efficient and effective use of resources enhance my service delivery	3.38
5	I meet work schedules on time	3.36
6	I have a sense of dependability and honesty	3.33
7	I work with others to achieve job duties	3.47
8	I perform duties assigned to me appropriately	3.44
9	In my library I set reasonable priorities for task completion	3.23
10	My problem solving ability enable me to attend to users needs	3.21
12	I perform job duties of others in their absence	3.12

GMWV	3.32
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Table 5 shows the summary of data collected on the contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria. The subjective notions of the respondents were converted to objective notions using Likerts scale conversion .Thereafter, the mean weight value method was used to determine relevant variables, and, doing so, variable whose mean is equal to or more than the GMWV is accepted to be relevant and vice versa (Sunmola, 2018).

With a GMWV = 3.32 the contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria include: the ability of the librarians to have a sense of dependability and honesty (MWV = 3.33), ability to attend to and solve users needs problems (MWV = 3.36), efficient and effective use of resources (MWV = 3.38), ability to perform duties assigned appropriately (MWV =3.44), ability to work with others as a team to achieve job duties (MWV =3.47), and ability to create new ideas to make service delivery easy (MWV =3.50) and punctuality at work and appointments (MWV = 3.32). These factors were accepted as contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria because their MWVs are more than the GMWV = 3.32.

But factors such as ability toperform the job duties of others in their absence (MWV = 3.12), ability to encourage colleagues to work and achieve quantity work output (MWV = 3.20), ability to meet work schedules on time (MWV = 3.21), ability to set reasonable priorities for task completion (MWV = 3.23) and, ability to be proficient in communication skills (MWV =3.28). These factors were rejected as contributions of Staff Training to Service Delivery of Librarians in Academic libraries in Ondo state, Nigeria because their MWVs are lesser to the GMWV = 3.32.

Presentation of Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: : There is no significant relationship between staff training and service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria.

This hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistical analysis. The summary of the resultof this analysis is as shown in Table

Table 6: Test of Relationship between Staff Training and Service Delivery in Academic Libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r.-value	P	Decision
Service Delivery	208	3 .32	0.350	0.335**	0.000	Ho is Rejected
Staff Training	208	3.27	0.467			

** Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Source: Computed Data, 2025_

Table6 shows that staff training has Mean = 3.27and SD = 0.467 while Service deliveryhas Mean = 3.32and SD = 0.350. Thus, a positive low correlation coefficient r = 0.335 and r²= 0.112 or 11.2% is found to be significant at P < 0.05, exists between staff training and service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The common types of training programmes available to library personnel in academic libraries in Ondo State are computer based training, Workshop and seminars, Self-instruction, Conferences attendance, Formal Professional library education. These types of training enhances the knowledge and skills of library staff, allowing them to introduce new services and improve existing ones (Nwosu and Ogbu (2019), allows staff to apply the knowledge gained immediately to their daily tasks, thus improving efficiency and service delivery (Aina, 2019) improve specialized services (Watson, 2020) and allow staff to learn at their own pace (Eze, 2020). Challenges of staff training in Academic Libraries in the study area include but not limited to; lack of financial resources, excessive workload and lack of interest of the management towards training programmes. These notions tally with Nwosu and Ogbu (2019), who noted that many academic libraries, particularly in developing countries, operate with limited budgets, which restricts their ability to invest in staff development. Aina (2019) further buttress this assertion by submitting that library staff often struggle to keep up with new digital tools and systems due to insufficient training necessary to handle new technologies or emerging trends in library science. As further lamented by Watson (2020), library personnel often have heavy workloads, which leaves little time for training and professional development and as found by Eze (2020) the foregoing make some library staff to always hesitant to adopt new technologies or service delivery models, leading to reduced service quality.

The aforementioned notwithstanding, training of library staff in the study area have led to increase in sense of dependability and honesty, ability to attend to and solve users needs problems, efficient and effective use of resources, ability to perform duties assigned appropriately and work with others as a team to make service delivery easy and punctuality at work and appointments. This observation is in consonance with the observation of Parasuraman et al (2018) who noted that service delivery in libraries is fundamentally about users comparing their expectations with their perceptions of the actual service received from librarians. The foregoing as succinctly suggested by Gyau et.al (2021) signifies that the quality of services delivered in the library is a predictor of overall service effectiveness. No wonder that Akpokodje and Lawal (2015) emphasize the need for libraries to always seek for ways to enhance their services constantly. This observation tallied with the notion of Akpokodje & Lawal, 2015) that competencies extends beyond traditional cataloging and reference services to include but not limited to expertise in managing digital collections, navigating complex databases, utilizing advanced search tools, and supporting users in accessing electronic resources, thus, in-house training, Coaching or mentorship and Study Visit training programmes should be made available to library personnel in academic libraries in Ondo State.

In addition, the extent to which library staff benefit from staff training in academic libraries in Ondo state are not significantly high. This assertion is in line with Johnson (2019) who succinctly mentioned that without proper investment in staff skill development, libraries may face challenges in fostering a motivated and competent workforce capable of proactively identifying and implementing new strategies to enhance service delivery.

As finally observed, a low positive correlation ($r = 0.335$ and $r^2 = 0.112$) that signified that staff training has about 11.2% variation on service delivery in academic libraries in Ondo State, Nigeria is a pointer to Awogbami et al (2021) assertion that Staff training is not a one-size-fits-all endeavor; it is customizable, with distinct section targeting different aspects of organization's needs, hence, continuous trainings that will keep library staff abreast of new developments will ensure that they remain competent and relevant in their field are needed in the study area.

Conclusion

Staff training is essential for improving service delivery in academic libraries hence, it should be improved on to enhances the technical skills, knowledge, and confidence of library personnel in the study area.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of this study, it is here by recommended that:

1. A wide awareness programmes should be designed to sensitize librarians for the need to always aspire for updating their knowledge about their services to library users.
2. Librarians should be encouraged to embark on skills acquisition programmessuch as coaching/mentorship, formal professional library education, study visit and self instruction methods.
3. Training of staff should be done from time to time or frequently provide to enhance librarian capacity so as to be abreast of acquiring current trends in library technology and applications
4. Librarians should be encouraged to attend training programmes organized for staff.
5. More librarian should be employed to curb excessive workload of Liberians

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